

The role of human resource management practices on the results of digitalisation. From Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0.

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The role of human resource management practices on the results of digitalisation.

From Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0

Abstract

Purpose: This article aims to analyse the impact of data analytics and robots on firms' performance across Europe.

Design/methodology/approach: To examine the impact of data analytics and robots on companies' performance, multilevel models are estimated. Empirical research is based on the fourth round of the European Company Survey 2019.

Findings: The main findings show that human resource management practices are relevant to explain firms' profits. Therefore, human resource practices and technology are complementary resources to achieve higher results. A positive and significant relation between profits and the use of data analytics to monitor employee performance was found. In addition, positive and significant relations between human resource practices and profitability were obtained.

Practical implications: From a practical perspective, this article helps us to understand the role of technological and human factors in profitability, and it emphasises the relevance of human resource strategies and technology to accomplish business outcomes.

Originality/value: Our findings reinforce the concept of Industry 5.0 which highlights the role of humans in the digitalisation process.

Keywords: Digitalisation; Automation; Data analytics; Human resource management practices; Economic results; Industry 5.0

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Introduction

The digital economy is having a great impact on the global economy; information and telecommunication technologies (ICTs) affect every industrial sector. At the same time, they transform social relationships, communications, education, jobs, and buying habits. In this context, firms realise that there is a need to adopt technologies in their business activities in order to meet their market demands. Big Data analytics, cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things, and system integration, among others, emerge to assist the production process and improve productivity. These technologies facilitate flexible production and enable the personalisation of products. Therefore, companies include digitalisation in their strategies to improve their results, growth, and productivity.

Employees are required to adapt their competencies to this new scenery, where digital skills are a key element to prosper in a digitalised economy and Industry 5.0. Human resources have a central role in the implementation of the digitalisation process, as employees' skills and engagement are crucial to succeed in this new framework. Even management should be different to support employees in this new environment (Greeven and Williams, 2017). As a result, human resource management practices (HRMP) affect the digitalisation process and can encourage employees to adopt technology or just to increase fears and distrust towards digitalisation.

The relevance of HRMP on the results of companies' digitalisation justifies the interest of the present research. Furthermore, although there is a set of case studies published about the digital process, there is not much empirical research based on datasets about digitalisation, to the best of our knowledge. This is precisely one of the main contributions of this paper.

This article presents an analysis of the impact of the use of ICTs on results and the role of HRMP across Europe. The empirical research is based on the fourth round of the European

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2
3 Company Survey 2019 developed by Eurofound and Cedefop. According to previous literature,
4
5 a positive effect of HRMP on the results of the company is expected (Eichhorst *et al.*, 2017;
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7 Bloom *et al.*, 2018).
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11 This research contributes to the study of digitalisation across Europe by 1) conducting a
12
13 systematic cross-national analysis including data from 35 countries and about 20,000
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15 establishments, 2) using new data from the European Company Survey 2019, 3) focusing on
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17 the relative contribution of human resource practices to the results of digitalisation, and 4)
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19 using empirical evidence from digitalisation rather than just case reports.
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23 **From Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0**

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26 The Industry 4.0 concept - also called "smart industry" - corresponds to new methods of
27
28 organising production, which seeks greater automation and, therefore, lower production costs
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30 (Edwards and Ramirez, 2016). The adaptation strategy towards the digital environment to
31
32 achieve Industry 4.0 is the digital transformation, which implies a connected industry in an
33
34 intelligent world (Erro-Garcés, 2021).
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38 Industry 4.0 implies changes in (a) the product; (b) the production processes, and
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40 consequently, (c) in the business model (Lu, 2017; Ghobakhloo, 2018). Moreover, machines
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42 are not the only key elements of Industry 4.0. The concept of Industry 4.0 has two aspects that
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44 feed its foundations: previous industrial revolutions, and the Internet of Things (IoT).
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48 A comprehensive transformation of the organization is required to achieve successfully the
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50 adaptation to Industry 4.0. In short, according to experts (Xu *et al.*, 2018), it is a change of
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52 mentality towards a culture that encourages continuous learning and innovation. Industry 4.0
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54 requires human-machine cooperation (Shi *et al.*, 2020). Its application affects, therefore, the
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56 organisation's human resources, and the style of leadership, which leads to a new paradigm;
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58 Industry 5.0.
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3 Industry 5.0 is defined as the penetration of Artificial Intelligence into common life. It
4 involves the cooperation between machines and humans with the objective of enhancing
5 humans' capacity and the return of humans' potential at the "Centre of the Universe" (Skobelev
6 and Borovik, 2017). In this sense, Industry 5.0 is a "human-centric solution": "while the main
7 concern in Industry 4.0 is about automation, Industry 5.0 will be a synergy between humans
8 and autonomous machines" (Nahavandi, 2019: p.3). Demir and Cicibaş (2018) and Demir *et*
9 *al.* (2019) also pointed out the human-robot coworking vision in Industry 5.0, and, even more,
10 they referred to organisational issues and the employees' perspective. However, the
11 implementation of Industry 5.0 presents several barriers at an organizational level (Mukherjee
12 *et al.*, 2023). In this context, Paschek *et al.* (2022) pointed out Society 5.0 and Leadership 5.0
13 as the path to the next industrial revolution, whereas Ghobakhloo *et al.* (2022) focused on the
14 potential of Industry 5.0 to promote sustainability.

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32 Finally, in the book "Strategizing AI in Business and Education: Emerging Technologies
33 and Business Strategy", Przegalinska and Jemielniak (2023) explored the implications of
34 emerging technologies such as IoT and robotics for business strategy and education. According
35 to their findings, IoT and robotics transform the way we work and learn. To quote an example
36 of the impact of these technologies at the workplace, robotics can be used to automate repetitive
37 or dangerous tasks, freeing up employees to focus on more creative or strategic work.
38 Przegalinska and Jemielniak (2023) argued that businesses and educators should embrace these
39 technologies and look for opportunities to leverage them to improve productivity, efficiency,
40 and innovation.

41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 **Hypothesis development** 54 55 56 57 58 59 60

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3 Digital transformation¹ implies the use of technology to change value chains. Big data
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5 analytics, robots, the Internet of the Things, and cybersecurity are becoming widespread
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7 instruments in the business context. According to Schweer and Sahl (2017), everything that
8
9 can be digitised will be digitised. Consequently, digitalisation can be considered a trend in the
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11 global economy (Kotarba, 2017). An analysis of the sales of robots indicates the growth of this
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13 industry. According to the International Federation of Robotics, the number of robots sold is
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15 increasing year by year. Whereas 113,000 units were supplied in 2008; 384,000 are expected
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17 in 2018. As intelligent robots are a crucial part of the digitalisation of the manufacturing
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19 industry, there is not just a significant rise in the number of robots put into operation but also
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21 an increasing number of new application areas (International Federation of Robotics, 2019).
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26 27 *Digitalisation and results*

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29 In today's global business environment, the implementation of data analytics or the use of
30
31 robots in companies leads to more competitive production processes or to increased service
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33 delivery. Thus, the main goals of digitalisation are related to the productivity and
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35 competitiveness of the companies. According to Parviainen *et al.* (2017), digitalisation implies
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37 the improvement of internal efficiency, the achievement of new external opportunities, and,
38
39 even more, the impact of digitalisation involves a disruptive change in the business. In this
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41 sense, it helps businesses more effectively change their company's business opportunities. For
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43 example, it may provide the possibility to offer new products and services to customers or to
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45 include relevant modifications in the value chain. New customers and therefore new sales can
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47 be achieved through digitalisation, apart from higher cross-sell ratios and a reduction of cost
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49 and operational issues, among other benefits (Gottlieb and Willmott, 2014; Desmet *et al.*, 2015,
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51 Schmidt *et al.*, 2015).
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¹ See Yokogawa (2021) to differentiate between digital transformation and digitalization

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3 Even more, one of the main reasons to engage in a digitalisation process is to improve the
4 productivity of a company. According to a study conducted by IDC and Microsoft in 2020,
5 companies that have adopted digital solutions such as AI, IoT, and cloud computing report 37%
6 higher revenue growth, 2.3 times higher employee productivity, and 4.4 times higher rates of
7 employee innovation and creativity than those that have not adopted such solutions.
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15 Measurements about digitalisation confirm the last statement and profitability indicators are
16 included in the key metrics on digitalisation. To quote an example, market-making metrics
17 confirm one of the variables considered in the McKinsey Global Institute Industry
18 Digitalization Index developed by Manyika *et al.* (2015). These metrics include revenues from
19 digitally enabled markets. Hence, additional indicators, such as the volume of product sales,
20 revenues, and the profitability of digital clients or the business activity generated via the mobile
21 and stationary channels, were appraised by Kotarba (2017) to complement the McKinsey
22 Global Institute Industry Digitalization Index. The most recent version of the index, released
23 in 2020, includes new indicators such as the use of artificial intelligence and the adoption of
24 cloud computing. In addition, the Digital Economy and Society Index developed by the
25 European Commission (2016) considers the labour productivity in ICTs and innovation and
26 patents related to digitalisation as relevant metrics to measure digitalisation. Precisely these
27 activities lead to major benefits and profitability.
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46 Along with this line, several case studies confirm the role of digitalisation in firms'
47 competitiveness. Bouwman *et al.* (2018), Ho and Lee (2015), Koch *et al.* (2019) and Parviainen
48 *et al.* (2017) among others, present the effects of digitalisation in different organisations
49 through case studies. These examples show the impact of digitalisation on companies. It
50 changes the strategy, affects the manner in which the company is organised, and even modifies
51 the business model. Nevertheless, most of the published case studies are not focused on the
52 influence of digitalisation on workers, which, under our perspective, would request more
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3 attention. In this sense, the case study conducted by Saari *et al.* (2016) about the situation of
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5 backstage workers in a specialised medical care organization in Finland showed how
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7 employees were motivated to design alternative futures for their work, and they were involved
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9 in designing them. In the same vein, Klumpp and Ruiner (2018) presented innovative food
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11 logistics solutions based on digitalised logistics that changed the organization of work and the
12
13 management of workers in food distribution.
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18 In fact, digitalisation can be considered a driver of competitiveness. Consequently, a
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20 positive relation between the use of robots, data analytics, and other sources of digital
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22 transformation and the results of a company can be expected. The following hypothesis is thus
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24 proposed:
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28 *H1:* Digitalisation has a positive effect on the results of a company because digital
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30 transformation increases productivity.
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32 33 *Workers against machines*

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36 Changes in the labour market imply new opportunities but also the destruction of traditional
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38 jobs. As a result, workers and unions have strongly opposed these innovations. This is not a
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40 new concern, as it has been going on for years. To quote an example, the so-called “Luddites”
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42 in the 18th century in the United Kingdom fought against textile machinery as they considered
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44 those machines a risk for employment (Hobsbawm, 1964). As a form of protest, they destroyed
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46 textile machines to protect domestic jobs, because some farmers worked at home in a rural
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48 industry to complement their earnings. Machines and factories were ascribed as a competitor
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50 to maintaining the mentioned rural life. Moreover, automation has been traditionally seen as a
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52 job destroyer, and the relationships between the automating process and the society’s well-
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54 being have been analysed (Rico, 1966).
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3 Gasparri and Tassinari (2020) point out at interventions of unions at the macro and meso
4 levels to create new forms of protection to deal with the effects of digitalisation. For that reason,
5 the impact of automation on labour markets and employment has attracted the interest of
6 academia. In this line, recent research has focused on these relationships between employment
7 and automation (Qureshi and Syed, 2014; Autor *et al.*, 2015; Leitão *et al.*, 2015).
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15 The question about whether automation is a contributor to unemployment has been studied
16 by scholars with different conclusions. Whereas several authors (e.g., Frey and Osborne, 2017;
17 Rajnai and Kocsis, 2017) concluded that the Smart Industry leads to a reduction in the number
18 of jobs, other research stated that Industry 4.0 reinforces competitiveness, which is needed for
19 the sustainability of companies and, consequently, employment (Acemoglu and Autor, 2011;
20 Ollo-López and Aramendia-Muneta, 2012). This favourable view is shared by Roblek *et al.*
21 (2016) who consider Industry 4.0 as the integration of a process that involves humans and
22 machines. Along with this line, Lasi *et al.* (2014) affirmed that new manufacturing systems
23 should respond to human needs and not the reverse, so the behaviour of employees is essential
24 to achieve the goals of Industry 4.0.
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39 On the other hand, working jointly with robots can induce stress in employees. Pollak *et al.*
40 (2020) pointed out the emotional, cognitive, and physiological reactions during the human-
41 robot collaboration, and highlighted the role of management and training to increase
42 employees' confidence in coping with the digital transformation.
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49 Considering the negative perspective of digitalisation on workers, HRMP can contribute to
50 lessening the resistance of employees to digital changes. On the other hand, organisational trust
51 should also be integrated into the analysis of HRMP. According to Tzafrir (2005), managers
52 are more likely to offer training and shape the internal promotion system when trust is high. In
53 this sense, employee-management trust has been shown to positively affect individual work
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3 performance and organisational commitment (Kramer and Tyler, 1999; Dirks and Ferrin, 2001;
4 Ferrin and Dirks, 2003). Consequently, the trust that an employee has in his or her superiors
5 could increase the effectiveness of HRM (Human Resources Management) practices (Innocenti
6 *et al.*, 2011). In addition, they found that firms exhibited higher performance when there is a
7 good relationship between management and employees. Even more, trust can be considered a
8 moderator between human resources practices and attitudes (Innocenti *et al.*, 2011). Therefore,
9 the following hypotheses are formulated:
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20 *H2a*: HRMP affect the outcomes of digitalisation.
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23 *H2b*: An employee-manager trustful relationship positively affects the company's results.
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26 *Training and development opportunities* 27

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29 It is widely recognised in the literature that training is the primary activity for having qualified,
30 adaptable, and well-prepared staff (Bartel, 1994; Raghuram, 1994; MacDuffie and Kochan,
31 1995). Therefore, companies need qualified workers to compete and therefore training and
32 development practices are a relevant variable associated with the results of the company
33 (Aragón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2003).
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41 In the realm of human resource management, training and development refer to the
42 deliberate and systematic efforts aimed at enhancing employees' knowledge, skills, and
43 attitudes to perform their current job roles or future responsibilities more effectively. Training
44 usually focuses on providing specific job-related skills, whereas development aims to foster
45 the employee's overall growth, preparing them for future leadership roles. With the rise of the
46 Fourth Industrial Revolution and the increased need for technological competencies,
47 organizations are becoming increasingly aware of the necessity of providing their employees
48 with relevant training and development programs. These programs often focus on the
49 acquisition of technical skills, such as data analytics or programming, as well as soft skills like
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3 critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability, which are becoming increasingly essential for
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5 success in the modern workforce.
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9 More recent studies (Muñoz Castellanos and Salinero Martín, 2011; Kim and Ployhart,
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11 2014) show that training programs increase motivation and boost firm performance. According
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13 to Úbeda García (2005), at the organizational level, training programs increase employee,
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15 customer, and shareholder satisfaction as well as improve business performance (i.e., sales per
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17 employee).
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20 From the perspective of the resource-based of the firm, training is included as an
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22 organization's resource that can give an advantage over competitors if the resource is unique
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24 and cannot be substituted. In this context, training can be seen as an investment in human
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26 capital that provides workers with new knowledge, skills and abilities that add value to the
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28 company and organizational outcomes (Ostroff and Bowen, 2000).
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32 On the other hand, some researchers such as Tharenou *et al.* (2007) and Thang *et al.* (2010)
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34 are more critical to the effects of training and development programs on the results of the
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36 company and there is an ongoing debate in the academia in this field.
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40 Based on the above, the following hypothesis is proposed:
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43 *H3: Training and development opportunities positively affect a company's economic*
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45 *results.*
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48 49 50 51 **Material and methods**

52 53 54 *Data*

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57 The data used in this empirical analysis come from the European Company Survey 2019
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59 (hereafter, ECS 2019) conducted by the European Foundation for the Improvement of Working
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3 and Living Conditions and Cedefop. More specifically, we use data from the last round of this
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5 survey (the fourth round).
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8 The dataset includes information about over 20,000 establishments across Europe. Given
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10 the nature of our research question, the research excludes not-for-profit organisations from the
11
12 sample (1,125 observations omitted).
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15 The data cover workplace practices such as work organisation, human resource
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17 management, skill use, skill strategies, digitalisation, direct employee participation, and social
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19 dialogue. This research focuses on skills and digitalisation data, although more information is
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21 also used as control variables.
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26 Surveys were developed by telephone to identify a management respondent. The average
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28 duration of the interview was 28 minutes, and the questionnaire was structured into 120 items.
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30 Subsequently, the questionnaires were filled out online. According to Eurofound, this approach
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32 reduces the burden on respondents, and it is expected to improve the quality of the responses.
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34 On the other hand, having the questionnaire administered fully online makes the ECS well and
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36 truly future-proof.
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40 In order to facilitate filling out the questionnaire, three different versions were adapted for
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42 (i) single independent companies with no subsidiary sites, (ii) subsidiary sites of multi-site
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44 companies, and (iii) headquarters of multi-site companies. Along with this line, definitions
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46 were included to gather comparable information.
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50 *Measures*

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53 Dependent variable: The dependent variable is a binary variable that measures whether the
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55 company made profits in 2018 (*In 2018, did this establishment make a profit?*). Value 1 implies
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57 that the company made profits, whereas value 0 indicates that they lost money or broke even.
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3 Independent variables: Independent variables include information about the digitalisation of
4 the company and HRMP. Concretely, binary variables measure the use of robots in the
5 company, the use of data analytics to improve the processes of production or service delivery,
6 and the use of data analytics to monitor employee performance.
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13 HRMP include information about practices related to the communication of a strong mission
14 and vision in a 1 to 4 Likert scale to measure the frequency of this communication. In addition,
15 the recruiting strategy is also considered in HRMP. A question that measures to what extent
16 the management looks internally to cover any new positions is included. This policy is
17 measured in a 1 to 5 Likert scale considering the frequency the managers look internally to
18 offer promotions.
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27 Concerning training strategies, the provision of opportunities for training and development
28 (1 to 4 scale) and their frequency are incorporated as an independent variable.
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33 Finally, the role of trust in the employee-manager relationship is crucial in HRM practices
34 (Tzafrir, 2005). A Likert variable that describes this relationship is included in the model (from
35 a very good to a very bad relation between management and employees).
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41 Control variables. Several control variables are included. As far as activity is concerned,
42 observations are classified in agriculture, industry, public administration and other services
43 from the NACE 1-digit code (Gooderham *et al.*, 2018), whereas company size is proxied by a
44 categorical variable with four categories structured by Eurofound (2016). The number of years
45 that the company has been carrying out the activity is also considered. Finally, country
46 dummies are included (Dølvik and Nergaard, 2011).
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55 Table I includes definitions of the variables as well as their means and standard deviations.
56 Table II presents the correlation matrix between the independent and dependent variables, and
57 their means and standard deviations. As can be observed in Table II, there are no high
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3 correlations between variables (less than 0.5). The highest correlation is presented between the
4 use of data analytics to improve the processes of production or the service delivery and the use
5 of data analytics to monitor employee performance, as both variables are related to data
6 analytics. For the rest of the variables, correlations are lower than 0.3.
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13 INSERT TABLE I AROUND HERE
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19 *Methods*

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21 Since the dependent variable (having or not having profits) is binary, probit models are used.
22 The first model just includes the control variables. Whereas in the second model, digitalisation,
23 HRMP, and continuous training variables are added. Finally, a model where the dependent
24 variable has to do with the implementation of data analytics to monitor performance is
25 estimated.
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33 **Results**

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35 Table III includes the results of univariate probit model estimations, where the results of the
36 company are considered to be the dependent variable. Cross-country weights were included in
37 the estimation to control for the different representativeness of the sample across countries.
38 The first column in Table III represents the model where just the control variables are
39 considered independent variables.
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52 The findings show a positive relationship between the size of a company and profitability,
53 as this is habitual in the literature (Ilaboya and Ohiokha, 2016; Hou and Van Dijk, 2018; among
54 others).
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3 With regard to the relationship between the age of a company and profitability, previous
4 literature shows an interesting debate. Whereas some scholars proved a positive and significant
5 relation between a firm's age and profitability (e.g., Halil and Hasan, 2012), other researchers
6 have described a negative relationship between age and profits (Dogan, 2013; Majumdar,
7 1997). In our case, this negative and significant relation has been reported, because the age of
8 the company variable is significant in all of the models, and all of them have negative
9 coefficients. Nevertheless, the referred variable that measures the age of the company is based
10 on the number of years that the company has been carrying out the activity. Consequently, this
11 variable can be related to the business cycle period or even to the innovation and creation of
12 new products and services in the company rather than the age of the company.
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27 Concerning the sector of activity, industry differences have also been found, and they point
28 to higher profitability for Construction than for Industry or Services. However, the variable
29 that represents the manufacturing companies is not significant ($p < 0.05$).
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34 Finally, significant differences across European countries were found. Macroeconomic
35 indicators (e.g., GDP growth, unemployment, evolution of wages, etc.) and, in fact, the
36 macroeconomic context might explain these differences.
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42 Column 2 in Table III shows the estimations when the digitalisation variables are included
43 in the model. Thus, the use of robots and the use of data analytics in the processes of production
44 or service delivery and the use of data analytics to monitor employee performance are added
45 to the model. The three digital tools present positive coefficients, just this last variable (the use
46 of data analytics in employee performance) reports a significant relationship with profitability.
47 Consequently, H1 (Digitalisation has a direct effect on the results of the company, as digital
48 transformation increases productivity) is just partially accepted, because just one of the digital
49 tools considered has a positive and significant relation with profitability.
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3 The next estimation (column 3) presents the model with the control variables and a
4 measurement of the use of data analytics to monitor employee performance. As expected, this
5 variable is positively and significantly linked to the probability of having profits.
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10 Then, human resources practices were incorporated to the model (column 4). In this sense,
11 a variable that measures to what extent the promotion of new positions is covered internally is
12 included. Additionally, the degree of opportunities provided for training and development is
13 also introduced in the model. Finally, the employee-manager relationship is also considered in
14 order to measure the employees' trust in management. As can be observed in Table III, all of
15 these variables have a positive and significant relationship with profitability. Consequently,
16 these factors increase the probability of obtaining profits in the company, and H2a, H2b and
17 H3 can be accepted. However, we need to highlight that it seems likely that training and
18 development importance may vary depending on the companies' engagement in revolutionary
19 industrial approaches (e.g., Boon *et al.*, 2019). Our database does not include this information,
20 consequently, we should accept partially H3.
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36 Finally, another model is considered in order to understand the relationships between
37 technology and profitability. In this case, the use of data analytics to monitor performance is
38 included as the dependent variable. As this is a binary variable, a probit model is also estimated.
39 Control variables, profitability, the use of robots, the use of data analytics in the production
40 process, and human resource practices, are included as independent variables. On this occasion,
41 the communication of a strong mission and vision is also included in the model as a variable
42 that represents the provision of providing meaning to the work. The results are shown in Table
43 IV (Column 1).
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56 INSERT TABLE IV AROUND HERE
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3 The variance explained in this model is much higher than the previous ones. There are also
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5 significant differences across countries. Nevertheless, the age of the company and the sector of
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7 activity do not report a significant relation with the use of data analytics to monitor employees'
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9 performance. As expected, the use of robots and the use of data analytics in the productive
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11 process present a positive and significant relation with the dependent variable. Also, providing
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13 opportunities for training and providing meaning to the work are positively and significantly
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15 related to the use of data analytics to monitor performance. The close relation between both
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17 uses of data analytics can result in statistical problems. Consequently, the same model was also
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19 estimated while dropping the variable that measures the use of data analytics in the production
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21 process. Column 2 in Table IV shows these results.
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27 In general terms, most results are similar to the last estimation, but differences between
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29 sectors are obtained in this model; industrial activities show the highest probability of using
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31 data analytics to measure performance. Additionally, a negative and significant relation with
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33 internal promotion is found, and a negative but not-significant relation with employee-
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35 management trust is obtained. The need for employees with new digital skills can result in new
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37 positions covered externally, which would explain the negative coefficient of the variable that
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39 measures internal promotion. In addition, these strategies would lead to a worse environment
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41 and that might explain the negative and significant coefficient of the variable that represents
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43 the relationship between managers and employees. Nevertheless, this last variable is negative
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45 but not significant.
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50 **Discussion**

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53 In explaining profitability, human resource practices seem to be relevant. According to our
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55 results, the use of robots or the use of data analytics in the productive process is not enough to
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57 understand the profitability of a company. Furthermore, a positive and significant relation
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3 between profits and the use of data analytics to monitor employee performance has been found.
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5 Along with this line, positive and significant relations between human resource practices and
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7 profitability were obtained.
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11 As a result, it can be concluded that technology facilitates human resource practices and,
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13 consequently, affects the results of a company. But it is essential to consider the role of
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15 employees and, particularly, the effect of human resource practices in this relationship. In this
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17 sense, technology can facilitate the implementation of human resource practices. For instance,
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19 as considered in the analysis, data analytics could be used to monitor employee performance.
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21 According to our results, precisely, the use of data analytics to monitor performance leads to a
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23 higher probability of obtaining profits in a company.
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27 Besides, the opportunity cost of using robots and conducting analytics related to the
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29 implementation of HR practices should go hand in hand in order to get the most out of ITCs.
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31 Otherwise, the investment in robots might affect the HR outcome. In this line, Demir *et al.*
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33 (2019) emphasise the relationship between co-working from the organizational and human
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35 employee's perspective and how this new vision is part of Industry 5.0 (Table V).
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INSERT TABLE V AROUND HERE

Regarding the role of human resource practices, the employee-manager relationship appears to be the main variable that positively affects the probability of obtaining profits. This result is coherent with previous literature, where trust has a relevant role in employee performance (Ferrin and Dirks, 2003; Tzafrir, 2005). Barriers to technological adoption can be overcome through the trust mentioned.

In addition, providing opportunities for training and development was positively and significantly related to profitability. Even more, after the employee-management relation, this is the main variable that affects the probability of obtaining profits. Specific training is required

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3 to integrate digital knowledge and to succeed in the new context where smart industries
4 substitute traditional factories (Benson *et al.*, 2002). Consequently, data science, math, and
5 advanced computer knowledge, among others seem to be essential in the Fourth Industrial
6 Revolution. In fact, these skills should be included in workers' curriculums, and educational
7 institutions should include them in youth training. In this context, a new employee profile has
8 appeared, the "Operator 4.0". The "Operator 4.0" was defined by Romero *et al.* (2016) as a
9 smart and skilled operator who performs 'work aided' by machines if and as needed. In this
10 line, new skills are required to adapt employees to the digitalised company (Erro-Garcés,
11 2021), and training is needed to acquire the new skills mentioned. Unfortunately, in our
12 database, it was not possible to identify the digital skills and training related to acquiring digital
13 competence. The availability of this information would improve these results.
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29 On the other hand, internal promotion as a strategy to cover new positions is positively and
30 significantly related to profitability. In fact, the analysis reinforces the role of the Human
31 Resources Department even in a digital context. In this line, several scholars (e.g., Nahavandi,
32 2019) refer to the new responsibilities of human resource departments in the digitalisation. To
33 quote an example, Human resource departments should decide which jobs will be handled by
34 robots (Nahavandi, 2019). Even more, Nahavandi (2019) suggests the need for a new name for
35 the human resource departments, because they will not just work with humans.
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46 **Conclusions**

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49 An empirical analysis of profitability factors was conducted on a large sample of European
50 companies. The research found a positive and significant relationship between HRMP and
51 profits, in addition to factors such as company age, size, and country differences. Our findings
52 reinforce the concept of Industry 5.0 (Demir *et al.*, 2019; Nahavandi, 2019), which emphasises
53 the importance of human involvement in the digitalisation process. Furthermore, the study is
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3 based on a large sample of information about digitalisation, making it a valuable resource for
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5 future research in this area.
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8 In the Industry 5.0 framework, cooperation between machines and human intelligence is
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10 crucial. According to our results, employees and practices to enhance their performance are the
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12 primary factors in increasing a company's profitability. Moreover, the use of technology (data
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14 analytics) to monitor performance was also found to be positively and significantly related to
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16 profitability.
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20 The research also identifies training as a critical factor in promoting the use of data analytics
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22 to measure performance. Thusly, Demir *et al.* (2019) also suggested that training is an
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24 important issue in the implementation of Industry 5.0, although the companies' engagement in
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26 industrial approaches should be considered (e.g., Boon *et al.*, 2019). Given the relevance of
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28 digital skills in the digitalisation process, exploring the role of skills in implementing Industry
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30 4.0 is an interesting area for future research.
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35 Trust in a human-robot co-working environment was identified as another critical factor
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37 (Demir *et al.*, 2019). The relationship between employees and managers, as well as employees'
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39 trust in management, may affect this human-robot trust. Therefore, there is a fruitful area for
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41 research based on the cooperation between technology and human resource practices. Further
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43 research can explore this relationship and consider the context of implementing Industry 5.0.
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47 From a practical perspective, this study helps us understand the role of technological and
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49 human factors in profitability, highlighting the importance of human resource strategies over
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51 technological ones. In short, our findings suggest that companies should prioritise their human
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53 resource strategies when it comes to enhancing profitability. In particular, companies should
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55 consider leveraging technology, such as data analytics, to monitor employee performance and
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57 support decision-making processes. Moreover, the paper emphasises the importance of trust
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3 and cooperation between human and machine intelligence. Companies can benefit from this
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5 finding by fostering a work environment that encourages collaboration and builds trust between
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7 employees and technology. By doing so, companies can leverage the strengths of both human
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9 and technological resources, resulting in increased profitability.
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13 Finally, as in every research project, this article presents several limitations. Our data
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15 included information about the profitability of a company through a binary variable (having
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17 losses or profits), but there was no further information about the evolution of the results or the
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19 quantity of funds obtained by the company. In addition, the level of debt affects profitability,
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21 and no specific data about the financial situation of the firm was available. Analysing a database
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23 with both economic and technological information about companies (use of robots, data
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25 analytics, automation, etc.) would lead to further results in this field. Hence, obtaining
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27 information about digital skills and the related training to acquire digital skills would be useful
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29 in a study of the requirements for employees in the digitalisation process. In addition, the use
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31 of robots and data analytics can be considered proxy variables of Industry 4.0. Nevertheless,
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33 robotics and automation technology are important drivers in achieving Industry 4.0, which
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35 justifies the use of our variables as proxies of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 (Bahrin *et al.*, 2016).
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Table I. Descriptive statistics

Variable		Observations	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Profitability						
Profits	<i>In 2018, did this establishment make a profit?</i>	20,112	0.786	0.410	0	1
Digitalisation						
use of robots	<i>Robots are programmable machines that are capable of carrying out a complex series of actions automatically, which may include interaction with people. Does this establishment use robots?</i>	19,216	0.119	0.324	0	1
data analytics in production process	<i>Does this establishment use data analytics to improve the processes of production or service delivery?</i>	20,592	0.498	0.500	0	1
data analytics to measure performance	<i>Does this establishment use data analytics to monitor employee performance?</i>	20,654	0.324	0.468	0	1
Human resources practices and training						
training and development opportunities	<i>Are opportunities provided for training and development?</i>	20,627	2.797	0.765	1	4

1							
2							
3							
4	internal promotion	<i>When recruiting, how often does management start by looking at</i>	20,605	2.243	1.236	1	5
5							
6		<i>whether there are any suitable internal candidates?</i>					
7							
8	employee-management relationship	<i>How would you describe the relations between management and</i>	20,623	4.067	0.664	1	5
9							
10		<i>employees in this establishment in general?</i>					
11							
12	giving meaning to work	<i>Is a strong mission and vision communicated to provide meaning to</i>	20,560	2.772	0.790	1	4
13							
14		<i>our work?</i>					
15							
16							
17							
18	Source: Authors' elaboration						
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Table II. Correlation matrix for profitability, digital variables, and human resource practices

	Mean	Standard deviation	profits	use of robots	data analytics in production process	data analytics to measure performance	training and development opportunities	internal promotion	employee-management relationship	giving meaning to work
Profits	0.786	0.410	1.000							
use of robots	0.119	0.324	0.023	1.000						
data analytics in production process	0.498	0.500	0.028	0.171	1.000					
data analytics to measure performance	0.324	0.468	0.036	0.103	0.432	1.000				
training and development opportunities	2.797	0.765	0.077	0.068	0.190	0.129	1.000			
internal promotion	2.243	1.236	-0.008	-0.076	-0.129	-0.078	-0.209	1.000		
employee-management relationship	4.067	0.664	0.091	-0.032	0.011	-0.009	0.217	-0.142	1.000	
giving meaning to work	2.772	0.790	0.042	0.027	0.159	0.122	0.431	-0.223	0.294	1.000

Table III. Probit estimations of profitability on digital tools and human resource practices

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Constant	3.240**	3.407***	3.520***	2.763**
	(1.182)	(1.229)	(1.237)	(1.248)
<i>Digitalisation</i>				
use of robots		0.009		
		(0.072)		
data analytics in production process		0.007		
		(0.044)		
data analytics to measure performance		0.106**	0.111**	0.085**
		(0.043)	(0.043)	(0.043)
<i>Human resources practices and training</i>				
training and development opportunities				0.130***
				(0.027)
internal promotion				0.044***
				(0.016)
employee-management relationship				0.141***
				(0.032)
giving meaning to work				
<i>Control variables</i>				
Size				
Medium	0.043	0.024	0.029	0.047
	(0.043)	(0.044)	(0.044)	(0.045)

1					
2					
3	Large	0.130**	0.098*	(0.113*	0.116*
4					
5		(0.055)	(0.058)	(0.057)	(0.059)
6					
7	Sector				
8					
9	Services	-0.168**	-0.172**	-0.178**	-0.141
10					
11		(0.069)	(0.075)	(0.074)	(0.075)
12					
13	Industrial	-0.121*	-0.128*	-0.136*	-0.140**
14					
15		(0.062)	(0.067)	(0.067)	(0.068)
16					
17	age of the Company	-0.001**	-0.001**	-.0015**	-0.002**
18					
19		(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	0.001)
20					
21	Country	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
22					
23					
24	Chi-2	348.07***	316.44***	314.48***	356.31***
25					
26	Pseudo R	0.0230	0.0238	0.0240	0.0344
27					
28	N	19,921	18,372	18,114	18,114
29					
30					

Standard errors in brackets.

* p < .10; ** p < .05; *** p < .01

Source: Authors' elaboration

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Table IV. Probit estimations. Dependent variable: Use of data analytics to monitor performance

	(1)	(2)
Constant	-3.639***	-3.525***
	(1.259)	(1.264)
<i>Profitability</i>		
profits		0.009
		(0.072)
<i>Digitalisation</i>		
use of robots	0.132**	0.247***
	(0.056)	(0.056)
data analytics in production process	1.139***	
	(0.042)	
<i>Human resources practices and training</i>		
training and development opportunities	0.118***	0.158***
	(0.028)	(0.026)
internal promotion	-0.017	-0.051***
	(0.017)	(0.016)
employee-management relationship	-0.036	-0.038
	(0.033)	(0.031)
giving meaning to work	0.087***	0.141***
	(0.028)	(0.026)
<i>Control variables</i>		
size		

Medium	0.162***	0.288***
	(0.047)	(0.043)
Large	0.062	0.317***
	(0.056)	(0.053)
sector		
Services	0.162***	0.187***
	(0.047)	(0.071)
Industrial	0.062	0.309***
	(0.056)	(0.066)
age of the company	0.001	0.001
	(0.001)	(0.001)
country	Yes	Yes
Chi-2	1,409.62***	1,351.00***
Pseudo R	0.1939	0.0731
N	18,114	18,114

Standard errors in brackets.

* $p < .10$; ** $p < .05$; *** $p < .01$

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table V. A comparison between Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0

	Industry 4.0	Industry 5.0
<i>Framework</i>	Machine-oriented	Human-centric solution
<i>Focus on</i>	Machines	Interaction between humans and machines
<i>Profitability based on</i>	Automation	HR practices (training and development opportunities and internal promotion) Trust
<i>The use of data analytics to monitor performance depends on</i>	The use of robots The use of data analytics in production process	The use of robots The use of data analytics in production process Training and development opportunities Giving meaning to work